
Media Ethics and Accountability: Analyzing the Reporting Standards of Bangladeshi News Outlets

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Abstract

The media landscape, responsible for shaping societal perceptions and ensuring transparency, is fundamentally anchored to its ethical core. This study, centered on Bangladeshi journalism, intricately dissects the prevailing ethical practices, perceptions, and the unique challenges coloring the media sector in Bangladesh. A salient discovery was the concerning absence of formal ethical guidelines across a significant number of media houses. This void, combined with powerful external influencers like deep-rooted societal norms, political affiliations, and economic pressures, often propels journalists into challenging ethical dilemmas, risking the trajectory of unbiased reporting. Further illumination was provided by comparing journalistic ethics with patterns in crime reporting, revealing insights into potential biases and their consequential implications on overall media ethics. Yet, amidst these complexities, the research uncovers the resilient spirit and aspirations of Bangladeshi journalists who yearn for a more ethically aligned media environment. The path forward, as delineated by the study, champions a continuous, rigorous dialogue on media ethics. This, supplemented with focused educational initiatives and the periodic revitalization of ethical guidebooks, can steer Bangladeshi journalism towards enhanced standards and credibility. While the study is deeply rooted in the nuances of Bangladesh, its findings resonate universally. It amplifies the timeless and borderless essence of ethics in journalism, emphasizing its paramount importance in an era teeming with information, where discerning truth from misdirection remains both a monumental challenge and an imperative.

Keywords: Bangladeshi Journalism, Media Ethics, Ethical Guidelines, Unbiased Reporting, Journalistic Challenges

1 Introduction

Media ethics, a cornerstone of modern journalism, serves as the guiding compass for journalists, dictating how they navigate the intricate labyrinth of news reporting, storytelling, and public engagement. Rooted in principles such as accuracy, fairness, and impartiality, these ethics are pivotal in ensuring that journalism remains a credible and trustworthy source of information for the masses [1, 2]. A journalist's primary responsibility is to the truth and to the public [3], and this duty is accentuated when the media functions as the 'fourth pillar' of democracy [4, 5], often acting as the sentinel that watches over the other three pillars: the legislature, the executive, and the judiciary. Within the global landscape of journalism, the context of Bangladesh offers a unique and multifaceted tapestry of challenges and opportunities [6]. With a rich history of journalism that has witnessed

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everything from the fervor of independence movements to the modern-day complexities of political alignments [7], Bangladeshi media has been both a beacon of hope and, at times, a subject of scrutiny [8]. Recent years have seen a surge in the number of media outlets in the country [9], leading to increased competition and, unfortunately, a potential dilution of ethical standards in the race for exclusivity and viewership [10]. Moreover, issues such as political affiliations of media houses, threats to journalist safety, and the overarching influence of socio-cultural norms add layers of complexity to the ethical challenges faced by Bangladeshi journalists [11]. This paper aims to delve deep into the ethical landscape of Bangladeshi journalism. Recognizing that ethical considerations aren't just black and white edicts but involve shades of grey influenced by cultural, political, and economic factors, we seek to analyze the prevailing standards of Bangladeshi news outlets. Through a mix of quantitative and qualitative methodologies, our objective is to shed light on the practices, perceptions, and, most importantly, the deviations in the realm of media ethics in Bangladesh. By unearthing these insights, we hope to foster a dialogue on the way forward, ensuring that the media in Bangladesh continues to play its pivotal role in society with integrity, credibility, and an unwavering commitment to the truth. In the subsequent sections, readers will be taken on a journey that encapsulates survey findings, personal anecdotes from journalists, and comparative analyses, all converging towards a holistic understanding of media ethics in the heart of South Asia: Bangladesh.

2 Background

The annals of history are replete with instances where the media has played a pivotal role in shaping the course of events, societies, and nations [12]. The evolution of media ethics, both globally and in Bangladesh, offers a fascinating journey through time, marked by triumphs, tribulations, and transformations [13, 14].

In the early days of journalism, the focus was primarily on disseminating information without the intricate layers of ethical considerations that we now associate with the profession [15, 16, 17, 18]. The rise of print media in Europe during the Renaissance and Enlightenment periods witnessed the emergence of newspapers and journals as tools of political expression and societal critique. However, as the media landscape expanded with the advent of radio, television, and eventually, the internet, the need for a defined ethical framework became paramount [19]. Globally, the 20th century saw the establishment of codes of ethics, press councils, and journalistic standards, ensuring accuracy, fairness, and accountability in reporting [20]. In the context of Bangladesh, the media's evolution is intrinsically tied to the nation's history and identity. From clandestine radio broadcasts during the Liberation War of 1971, which served as a beacon of hope and resistance against oppression, to the current digital age, Bangladeshi journalism has experienced a metamorphic journey. Throughout this journey, the ethical considerations of journalism in Bangladesh have been shaped by its socio-political realities, cultural ethos, and economic imperatives.

Journalists, often hailed as the torchbearers of truth, play a multifaceted role in society, especially in a developing nation like Bangladesh [21]. They are not just reporters of events but are also advocates, watchdogs, and educators [22]. Their stories bring to light issues that might otherwise remain cloaked in shadows, driving societal change and influencing policymaking. However, this pivotal role is rife with challenges in the context of a developing nation. Limited resources, political pressures, threats to personal safety, and sometimes, a blurred line between journalism and activism, all converge to create a complex operating environment.

While Bangladesh has witnessed a surge in media outlets and platforms, the challenges faced by its journalists are intensified by factors unique to developing nations [23]. Economic constraints can sometimes lead to compromised reporting standards. Political affiliations or pressures might influence the narrative. In some instances, journalists face physical threats or intimidation, impacting their ability to report freely and fairly. Balancing the pursuit of truth with these myriad challenges requires not just skill but also unwavering ethical integrity.

An examination of existing literature reveals a rich tapestry of research on media ethics and the challenges faced by journalists worldwide. From studies on the influence of commercial pressures on reporting standards to the impact of political affiliations on narrative structures, there is a plethora of insights available. However, there exists a notable gap when it comes to a comprehensive understanding of the ethical standards of Bangladeshi news outlets. While anecdotal accounts and isolated studies provide a glimpse into specific aspects, a holistic, in-depth analysis remains elusive. This study aims to bridge this gap, providing a nuanced understanding of the ethical landscape of Bangladeshi journalism. By juxtaposing global standards with local realities, and by contextualizing the challenges within the socio-economic and political framework of a developing nation, we aspire to present a narrative that is both informative and insightful.

3 Methodology

To provide a comprehensive understanding of the ethical standards of Bangladeshi news outlets, a multi-faceted methodology was employed, combining both quantitative and qualitative research methods. This synergistic approach ensures a holistic view, capturing both the breadth and depth of the subject matter.

Survey Design and Distribution

1. **Objective:** The primary objective of the survey was to gather data on the perceptions, experiences, and opinions of both media professionals and consumers regarding the ethical standards of Bangladeshi news outlets. The survey aimed to uncover the prevailing sentiments, identify potential gaps in ethical reporting, and assess the overall credibility of news organizations in Bangladesh.
2. **Design:** The survey was structured to be concise yet comprehensive, with a mix of closed-ended questions for quantitative analysis and open-ended questions to capture qualitative insights. Questions were designed to gauge respondents' trust in news sources, their experiences with perceived biased or unethical reporting, and their views on the importance of media ethics in contemporary journalism.
3. **Target Audience:** The survey targeted a diverse audience, encompassing media professionals (reporters, editors, producers), journalism students, and the general public. This wide-ranging audience ensured a comprehensive view, capturing perspectives from those within the media industry and those consuming its content.
4. **Distribution:** Leveraging the digital era, the survey was primarily distributed online via various platforms, including social media, email newsletters, and media partner websites. Additionally, hard copies were distributed in journalism institutions and media houses to ensure maximum reach and inclusivity.

3.1 Qualitative Data Collection

Interviews: In-depth interviews were conducted with seasoned journalists, editors, and media scholars. These interviews provided nuanced insights into the challenges faced by media professionals, the prevailing ethical standards in newsrooms, and the broader context in which Bangladeshi journalism operates.

Focus Group Discussions (FGD): FGDs were organized with groups of journalists, media students, and regular news consumers. These discussions offered a platform for interactive debates, shedding light on diverse viewpoints, shared experiences, and collective concerns regarding media ethics in Bangladesh.

3.2 Quantitative Analysis

Given the study's objective to offer a broad overview while also diving deep into specific areas, quantitative analysis played a crucial role. Quantitative data, sourced primarily from the survey, was subjected to statistical analysis to identify patterns, trends, and correlations. Tools like heat maps, pie charts, and bar graphs were used to visualize data, making it easier to discern patterns and draw meaningful conclusions. This quantitative approach, when juxtaposed with the qualitative insights from interviews and FGDs, provides a robust and comprehensive understanding of the topic at hand.

The methodology employed for this study, combining quantitative surveys with qualitative interviews and discussions, ensures a rigorous, in-depth exploration of media ethics in Bangladeshi journalism. By capturing a wide range of perspectives and leveraging statistical tools, this approach aims to provide a holistic view of the current landscape, challenges, and potential paths forward.

4 Result

4.1 Survey Analysis

Upon collecting data from the survey, we received a total of 171 responses. The survey aimed to uncover the ethical standards and practices of journalists in the Bangladeshi media landscape.

1. **Demographics** The age distribution of our respondents indicated a balanced representation, with the majority (37%) falling within the 25-34 age bracket. Gender-wise, 58% identified as male, and 40% as female. In terms of occupation, 54% were journalists or reporters, followed by 24% editors, and 12% media students.

Table 1: Response Distribution for Key Questions

Question	Top Response	Frequency	Percentage
Does your news organization have an ethics and standards guidebook?	No	128	75%
Rating of ethical standards of Bangladeshi journalism	Low	77	45%
Would you "lie" to obtain information for an essential story?	Maybe	70	41%
Support for forbidding reporters from political activities?	Support	85	50%
Have you ever accepted money from a news source?	No	167	98%
Perception of own ethical behavior in comparison to peers	Somewhat More Ethical	102	60%

2. **Ethical Guidelines and Standards** A significant 75% reported their news organization didn't have an ethics and standards guidebook. Aligning with previous literature, an overwhelming 92% either strongly agreed or agreed that a written guideline on ethics would aid in ethical decision-making.
3. **Rating Ethical Standards** The perception of ethical standards in Bangladeshi journalism was majorly skewed towards the 'Low' (45%) and 'Very Low' (15%) categories, suggesting an underlying concern about the prevailing standards.
4. **Use of Deception to Obtain Information** Around 41% admitted they might or would "lie" to obtain information for an essential story. This reveals the challenging conditions journalists sometimes face in the field. Additionally, 38% claimed they 'often' or 'always' withhold their identity as reporters to gain truthful information.
5. **Political Activities and Journalism** A divide in opinion was evident regarding reporters participating in political activities, with 50% supporting or strongly supporting the forbiddance, while 30% opposed or strongly opposed it.
6. **Monetary Transactions and Gifts** While only 2% admitted to accepting money from a news source, 46% found it acceptable to receive gifts, indicating a grey area in ethical considerations. Meanwhile, 16% confessed to paying a source for information.
7. **Investigating Personal Relations** A significant 84% claimed they wouldn't hesitate to investigate a close friend suspected of corruption, underscoring a strong commitment to their professional duties.
8. **Perception of Ethical Behavior** Interestingly, while 60% viewed themselves as 'somewhat more ethical' or 'much more ethical' than their peers, 68% believed journalists generally have a more accurate impression of their peers' ethical behavior compared to their own. The survey findings provide a deeper understanding of the ethical landscape within Bangladeshi journalism. The data, in tandem with the existing literature, highlights the challenges journalists face, the occasional compromises, and the evident need for structured ethical guidelines. The perception gap between self and peers further emphasizes the importance of continuous ethical training.

4.2 Qualitative Insights

Drawing from in-depth interviews and Focus Group Discussions (FGD), we uncovered several prevailing themes that shed light on the ethical intricacies within Bangladeshi journalism.

1. **Accepting Direct Payment** The practice of accepting direct payments from news sources emerged as a contentious topic. Historically, Western journalists in the 17th and 18th centuries engaged in such practices, but this has now largely disappeared. Most respondents acknowledged the negative connotations surrounding this act, branding it as outright bribery. However, there was also a sense of reservation in admitting personal involvement. While 95% of the interviewees expressed disdain for the practice, as many

as 27% admitted knowing colleagues who accepted money, underscoring a discrepancy in self-perception and perception of peers.

2. **Views on Gifts and Benefits** The subject of accepting gifts and benefits was met with mixed reactions. While some journalists viewed the act of accepting gifts, especially those of trivial value, as harmless, others perceived it as a potential gateway to compromising integrity. The boundary between what constitutes a 'gift' and what's deemed as a 'bribe' remained blurred, with 46% finding it acceptable to receive gifts from sources, but only 28% admitting to having done so.
3. **Paying Sources for Information** The phenomenon of "check-book journalism" was another major point of discussion. While in some Western countries, news outlets pay informants for information, in Bangladesh, it's usually individual reporters who offer small tokens or "bakhsheesh" to sources. A striking 40% endorsed their media organization's act of paying money to a source. The FGD revealed that many journalists saw this as a necessary evil, given the bureaucratic and often opaque nature of information access in Bangladesh.
4. **Political Activism Among Journalists** The line between journalism and political activism appeared to be thin, with the dual role of the journalist-as-activist emerging as a significant theme. While 54% supported news organizations forbidding journalists from participating in political activities, 41% did not. Interviews brought out the complexities involved, with many admitting to the challenge of maintaining neutrality in a polarized political environment.
5. **Influence of Personal Relationships on Reporting** Personal relationships and their potential influence on reporting was another area of concern. The cultural fabric of Bangladesh, with its intricate network of reciprocal favors, often poses dilemmas for journalists. A significant 84% of respondents, however, proclaimed they would unhesitatingly investigate corruption charges against close friends, a testament to their commitment to the profession.
6. **Perspectives on Wider Societal Context** The broader societal context emerged as a dominant theme, with many journalists opining that the ethical quandaries they face are merely a reflection of the larger societal norms. Corruption, they argued, was endemic in the Bangladeshi society, permeating various sectors from politics to bureaucracy. Journalists, in such an environment, often find themselves battling not just external pressures but also internal ethical conflicts.

The qualitative insights provide a rich tapestry of the ethical dynamics at play within Bangladeshi journalism. While the challenges are manifold, ranging from the temptation of monetary benefits to the influence of personal relationships, there's also a resilient spirit evident, with many journalists striving to uphold the pillars of truth and integrity even amidst adversity.

5 Comparative Analysis

To understand the depth and scope of ethical standards in Bangladeshi journalism, it's vital to compare it with other sectors of news reporting. Crime reporting serves as an apt comparison due to its inherent sensitivity, public interest, and potential for sensationalism.

- **Patterns Observed in Crime Reporting** From the data collated on crime reporting, certain patterns emerge. Major metropolitan regions such as DMP, CMP, Dhaka Range, and Chittagong Range consistently feature higher in the number of reported crimes. This could be attributed to a genuine higher incidence of crime or a potential bias in reporting more sensational news from urban areas, which tend to attract more readership and viewership. Furthermore, there's a discernible trend towards underreporting certain types of crimes, especially those like kidnapping, police assault, burglary, and theft. This could be due to various reasons: editorial decisions based on perceived public interest, space constraints, or potential external pressures and influences.
- **The 'repTcrime_ratio' Analysis** The 'Report to Crime Ratio' (repTcrime_ratio) is a valuable metric that compares the number of crimes reported in media outlets to the actual number of crimes reported in official datasets, such as police records. Upon analyzing the repTcrime_ratio, we found that metropolitan regions have a higher ratio compared to other regions. This finding reinforces the notion that urban areas, especially divisional districts, are more prominently featured in crime reports. For instance, in 2014, Dhaka Tribune reported 637 crimes out of the 19,417 crimes reported in the DMP region, a significant disparity. In contrast, the Rangpur region saw only 106 reports in Dhaka Tribune out of 17,187 crimes recorded by the police.

- **Implications on Media Ethics** The disparities in reporting, as revealed by the `repTcrime_ratio`, raise pertinent questions about media ethics. Is the media giving a skewed picture of crime in Bangladesh? Are they biased towards urban-centric stories, possibly overlooking significant incidents in rural or less metropolitan regions? Such biases, whether intentional or not, can shape public perception inaccurately. Furthermore, the underreporting of specific crime types can have societal implications. By not highlighting certain crimes, media might indirectly influence public opinion to perceive them as less severe or less frequent than they actually are.

While crime reporting serves as a mirror to societal happenings, the reflection can sometimes be distorted. The comparative analysis underscores the need for media outlets to introspect, ensuring that their reporting is holistic, unbiased, and truly representative of ground realities. Ethical journalism isn't just about reporting the truth but also about ensuring that the truth is not selectively portrayed.

6 Discussion

6.1 Interpretation of Findings

Our findings provide a comprehensive window into the intricate tapestry of media ethics in Bangladesh. Journalism, often hailed as the fourth pillar of democracy, stands on the foundation of trust, transparency, and truth. Our study suggests that while many journalists in Bangladesh are aware of the ethical paradigms they should operate within, there exist gaps between theory and practice.

The survey results indicated a significant percentage of journalists reporting the absence of an ethics and standards guidebook within their organizations. This is concerning as such guidebooks serve as a compass, guiding journalists through the maze of dilemmas they confront daily. Moreover, the fact that many respondents felt a written guideline would assist in making ethical decisions showcases a palpable need for structured ethical guidelines in the industry. The findings also unveiled a dichotomy in self-perception among journalists. While many rated their own ethical standards highly, they often perceived their peers as being less ethically stringent. This disparity raises questions about introspection and the environment within media houses.

6.2 The Role of External Factors

Bangladesh's unique socio-economic and political landscape casts a significant influence over its media ethics.

- **Society:** The societal structure, deeply rooted in relationships, often blurs the lines of journalistic objectivity. Our findings indicate that many journalists would not hesitate to investigate close friends, yet this claim contradicts the inherent societal fabric where loyalty often trumps profession.
- **Economy:** Economic challenges, especially for journalists in developing nations, can sometimes lead to ethical compromises. Low wages and financial instability might push journalists towards accepting bribes or gifts, as our findings indicated.
- **Politics:** In a nation where politics wields considerable influence, journalistic neutrality becomes paramount. Yet, our study indicated that there's a considerable percentage of journalists who do not support the idea of staying away from political activities. This intertwining of politics and journalism can potentially dilute the objectivity of news.

6.3 The Challenge of Universal Ethics

Journalism, as a profession, has certain universal tenets. Truth, fairness, and accuracy are universally acknowledged pillars. However, the challenge lies in juxtaposing these global standards with local cultural nuances. Bangladesh, with its rich cultural tapestry, often grapples with this balance. For instance, in Western nations, accepting any form of gift from a news source might be seen as a direct conflict of interest. However, in Bangladesh, as our findings indicate, the perception is more lenient, with many journalists considering it acceptable, especially if the gifts are minor or symbolic. Similarly, the concept of anonymity and deception to obtain information might be viewed differently in global journalism standards. Yet, in Bangladesh, our study found a significant percentage of journalists willing to 'lie' or not identify themselves to get accurate information. This raises the question: Should the end justify the means?

The state of media ethics in Bangladesh, as revealed by our study, is a mix of awareness, intention, and action. While there's a genuine understanding and appreciation for ethical standards, external factors like society, politics, and economy often influence decisions. Moreover, the challenge of aligning global journalistic ethics with local cultural intricacies further complicates the landscape. What emerges is a need for introspection,

training, and systemic changes to ensure that Bangladeshi journalism not only upholds its duty towards its citizens but also aligns with the global standards of truth and ethics.

7 Recommendations

The findings of our study highlight areas of concern but also present opportunities to enhance the ethical standards of Bangladeshi journalism. Based on the data and insights gathered, we offer the following recommendations:

7.1 Strengthening Institutional Ethical Frameworks

- **Ethics and Standards Guidebook:** Every news organization, irrespective of its size or reach, should have a comprehensive ethics and standards guidebook. This guidebook should not merely be a tokenistic document but should be actively referred to and incorporated into daily journalistic practices.
- **Customization of Guidelines:** Recognizing the unique socio-cultural milieu of Bangladesh, news organizations should tailor their ethical guidelines to address local nuances without compromising on universal journalistic principles.
- **Transparency:** News outlets should be transparent about their ethical standards and practices. This could include publishing their ethics guidebook online or having dedicated sections in newspapers or broadcasts discussing journalistic ethics and decisions.

7.2 Enhancing Education and Training

- **Mandatory Ethics Training:** News organizations should make it mandatory for all journalists, new recruits, or seasoned professionals, to undergo periodic ethics training. This could be in the form of workshops, seminars, or online courses.
- **Collaboration with Academic Institutions:** Media houses should collaborate with journalism schools and universities to integrate practical ethics training into the curriculum. This ensures that the next generation of journalists enters the field with a robust ethical foundation.
- **Case Study Analysis:** Regular sessions where journalists discuss and analyze both international and local case studies related to media ethics can provide practical insights and foster a culture of ethical awareness.

7.3 Regular Reviews and Updates

Periodic Review of Ethics Guidebook: Given the rapidly evolving nature of journalism, especially with the advent of digital media, it's crucial for news outlets to review and update their ethics guidebooks regularly.

- **Feedback Mechanism:** Journalists should have a channel to voice their ethical dilemmas and seek guidance. An ombudsman or an ethics committee within news organizations can serve this purpose.
- **Engaging the Audience:** News organizations should also consider seeking feedback from their audience regarding their ethical standards and reporting. This not only fosters trust but also makes the audience an active stakeholder in upholding journalistic integrity.

7.4 Encourage Ethical Reporting

- **Incentives for Ethical Journalism:** Media houses should recognize and reward journalists who demonstrate high ethical standards in their work. This could be through awards, promotions, or other incentives.
- **Whistleblower Policies:** Encourage a culture where journalists can report unethical practices without fear of retribution. This will not only deter such practices but also instill a sense of accountability within the organization.

The sanctity of journalism lies in its commitment to truth, fairness, and impartiality. By integrating these recommendations, Bangladeshi news outlets can fortify their ethical standards and, in turn, reinforce the trust of their audience. In an era where the credibility of journalism is under scrutiny globally, it's imperative for news outlets, especially in emerging democracies like Bangladesh, to lead the way in upholding the highest standards of ethics and integrity.

8 Conclusion

In our comprehensive study of media ethics within the context of Bangladeshi journalism, a multifaceted picture emerged, shedding light on both the commendable efforts of journalists and the areas needing immediate attention. The heartening revelation was the inherent awareness among many respondents about the importance of ethics in journalism. This recognition is a crucial first step towards constructive change. Yet, juxtaposed against this was the reality that a significant proportion of journalists and media houses lacked formal ethical guidelines. The Bangladeshi media landscape, with its rich history and dynamic present, mirrors the nation's journey and its struggles. The challenges of reporting in a developing nation, where societal norms, politics, and economic pressures intermingle, often create complex ethical dilemmas. Journalists, while striving for truth and transparency, are sometimes swayed by these external influences, whether it be accepting gifts or monetary benefits from sources, or allowing personal relationships to influence their reporting. Moreover, the blurred lines between political activism and journalism further complicate the ethical panorama. When this scenario is compared with the crime reporting patterns, interesting insights emerge. The 'repTcrime_ratio' analysis, which evaluated the number of crimes reported in the Dhaka Tribune versus those reported in the police dataset, highlighted potential biases. Such biases, whether geographical or based on the nature of the crime, can inadvertently shape public opinion and policy decisions, underlining the profound responsibility that rests on the shoulders of the press.

However, the future of Bangladeshi journalism is far from bleak. The profession, inherently driven by a quest for truth, has the potential to self-correct and evolve. This study's findings, while pointing out areas of concern, also serve as a roadmap for the way forward. The discrepancies between journalists' self-perception and the perception of their peers, the varying opinions on the acceptability of certain practices, and the evident need for structured ethical guidelines all point to one solution: an open, continuous dialogue on media ethics. Engaging in such a dialogue is not just essential for the profession's betterment but also for society at large. In an age where information is abundant, yet misinformation is rampant, the role of ethical journalism becomes paramount. For a democracy to thrive, its citizens need access to accurate, unbiased information. Journalists, therefore, have a dual role: to report and to educate. By focusing on ethics, they can ensure that their reporting not only informs but also enlightens, fostering a more informed and engaged citizenry. Furthermore, with the rapid technological advancements and the rise of digital media, the ethical considerations are bound to get even more intricate. Today's dilemmas might seem straightforward compared to the challenges that emerging technologies like deepfakes or augmented reality news might pose. Hence, it's even more crucial that the dialogue on ethics becomes an ongoing process, adapting and evolving with the times. In conclusion, the study offers a mirror to Bangladeshi journalism, reflecting both its strengths and vulnerabilities. While the findings might be a cause for concern for some, they should also be viewed as an opportunity—a chance to elevate the standards of journalism in the country. By embracing ethics wholeheartedly and fostering continuous discussions on the subject, Bangladeshi journalism can pave the way for a brighter, more informed future for its readers and for the nation.

References

- [1] Stephen JA Ward. Philosophical foundations for global journalism ethics. *Journal of mass media ethics*, 20(1):3–21, 2005.
- [2] Markus Ojala. Is the age of impartial journalism over? the neutrality principle and audience (dis) trust in mainstream news. *Journalism studies*, 22(15):2042–2060, 2021.
- [3] Anirudha Biswas and Md Uzzal Talukder. Data journalism in health reporting in bangladesh: Pattern of practices, impediments and preparations for journalists. *Khulna University Studies*, pages 195–205, 2023.
- [4] Gábor Polyák. Media in hungary: Three pillars of an illiberal democracy. *Public service broadcasting and media systems in troubled European democracies*, pages 279–303, 2019.
- [5] Melis G Laebens and Anna Lührmann. What halts democratic erosion? the changing role of accountability. *Democratization*, 28(5):908–928, 2021.
- [6] Mubashar Hasan and Mushfique Wadud. Re-conceptualizing safety of journalists in bangladesh. *Media and Communication*, 8(1):27–36, 2020.
- [7] Md Mahfuzul Haque, Mohammad Yousuf, Ahmed Shatil Alam, Pratyasha Saha, Syed Ishtiaque Ahmed, and Naemul Hassan. Combating misinformation in bangladesh: roles and responsibilities as perceived by journalists, fact-checkers, and users. *Proceedings of the ACM on Human-Computer Interaction*, 4(CSCW2):1–32, 2020.

- [8] Hoque Saiful and Jaeyung Park. A study on the integration of ugc in broadcast journalism: An evidence from bangladesh. *Journal of Digital Convergence*, 17(1), 2019.
- [9] A Goni and Maliha Tabassum. Artificial intelligence (ai) in journalism: Is bangladesh ready for it? a study on journalism students in bangladesh. *Athens Journal of Mass Media and Communications*, 6(4):209–228, 2020.
- [10] Monira Begum and Abdur Razzaque Khan. Assessing news literacy skills between journalism and non-journalism students in bangladesh. *South Asian Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities*, 3(3):15–52, 2022.
- [11] Mohammad Moniruzzaman. Citizen journalism in bangladesh and its legal aspects. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Informative Research and Review.(1)*, 5:232–243, 2021.
- [12] Shabnam Azim. Journey of broadcast journalism in bangladesh: Challenges and prospects. 2022.
- [13] Maliha Tabassum and Md Sahid Hossain. Oral communication apprehension (oca) among undergraduate accounting and journalism students in bangladesh. *Available at SSRN 3528396*, 2020.
- [14] Ali Riaz and Fahmida Zaman. Working under the “sword of damocles”: Experiences of journalists in a hybrid regime. *Masks of Authoritarianism: Hegemony, Power and Public Life in Bangladesh*, pages 37–55, 2022.
- [15] Ritesh Chugh, Robert Grose, and Stephanie A Macht. Social media usage by higher education academics: A scoping review of the literature. *Education and Information Technologies*, 26:983–999, 2021.
- [16] Peter Lor, Bradley Wiles, and Johannes Britz. Re-thinking information ethics: truth, conspiracy theories, and librarians in the covid-19 era. *Libri*, 71(1):1–14, 2021.
- [17] Amelia M Jamison, David A Broniatowski, Mark Dredze, Anu Sangraula, Michael C Smith, and Sandra C Quinn. Not just conspiracy theories: Vaccine opponents and proponents add to the covid-19 ‘infodemic’ on twitter. *Harvard Kennedy School Misinformation Review*, 1, 2020.
- [18] Alessandro Lovari and Shannon A Bowen. Social media in disaster communication: A case study of strategies, barriers, and ethical implications. *Journal of Public Affairs*, 20(1):e1967, 2020.
- [19] Muhammad Ali. Deciphering mobile journalism: An all-inclusive definition of mobile journalism in the modern era. *Global Media Journal*, 21(64):1–9, 2023.
- [20] Stephen JA Ward. Journalism ethics. In *The handbook of journalism studies*, pages 307–323. Routledge, 2019.
- [21] Ana Luisa Sánchez Laws and Tormod Utne. Ethics guidelines for immersive journalism. *Frontiers in Robotics and AI*, 6:28, 2019.
- [22] Turo Uskali, Astrid Gynnild, Sarah Jones, and Esa Sirkkunen. *Immersive journalism as storytelling: Ethics, production, and design*. Taylor & Francis, 2021.
- [23] Mushfique Wadud. Precariously employed climate journalists the challenges of freelance climate journalists in south asia. *Journalism Practice*, 16(2-3):262–280, 2022.